

Quasi-SMILES based QSPR models for Adsorption energies and catalytic activity of Ziegler – Natta catalysts for propylene polymerization

P. Ganga Raju Achary^{1*}, Sanija Begum, Alla P. Toropova,²Andrey A. Toropov²

¹ *Department of Chemistry, Institute of Technical Education and Research(ITER), Siksha 'O' Anusandhan University,Bhubaneswar,Odisha-751030(India)*

²*IRCCS-Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, Via La Masa 19, 20156 Milan, Italy*

Published version of this paper could be find here

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.md.2016.12.003>

Materials Discovery Volume 5, August 2016, Pages 22-28

*Address for correspondence:

Assistant Professor in Chemistry,

Institute of Technical Education and Research (ITER), Siksha 'O' Anusandhan University, Khandagiri, Bhubaneswar, Odisha-751030 (India)

Office Phone: +91-674-2350181, 2351539. 2351777, 2351419

Fax: +91-674-2351880/2351217

E-mail: pgrachary@soauniversity.ac.in

Abstract

A heterogeneous Ziegler–Natta (ZN) catalyst has been the first choice in the olefin polymerization industries. The electron donors play a major role in the ZN catalyzed polypropylene polymerization. Quasi-SMILES based QSPR models are explored for the prediction of adsorption energies and catalytic activities of three types of internal electron donors, phthalates, 1, 3-diethers and malonates compounds. The adsorption energy and polypropylene activity has been modelled with three random splits with the representations of the molecular structure by quasi-simplified molecular input line entry system. The QSPR model building is done by the Monte Carlo optimization using three methods classic scheme (*CS*), balance of correlations (*BC*) and balance of correlation with ideal slopes (*BCIS*). The best model for the adsorption energy could be obtained from the random split-2 by *BC* method, for the training set ($r^2=0.999$, $q^2=0.998$), calibration set ($r^2=0.998$, $q^2=0.998$), validation set ($r^2=0.926$, $q^2=0.834$) and for the invisible validation set ($r^2=0.876$, $q^2=0.863$). The robustness of these quasi-SMILES based QSPR models are further checked by external validation parameters as r_m^2 , r_m^{*2} and randomization technique. The quasi-SMILES based QSPR model successfully applied for designing new internal donors for the ZN catalyzed propylene polymerization.

Keywords: Propylene polymerization; Quantitative structure–property relationships; Quasi-SMILES, adsorption energies; optimal descriptor

1. Introduction

Today in the olefin polymerization industries heterogeneous Ziegler – Natta (ZN) catalysts are first choice and generally the commercial catalysts obtained by modifying the parent Ziegler – Natta system in the manufacture of polypropylene (PP)[1,2]. The catalyst comprises of the $MgCl_2$ -supported $TiCl_4$ catalyst in conjunction with

triethylaluminium [Al(C₂H₅)₃] as co-catalyst and organic additives (electron donors) for the production of isotactic polypropylene. These electron donors can be internal donors (which are added during the catalyst preparation) or external donors for the propylene polymerization process[2]. The earlier study shows that the internal electron donors are better than the external donors[2]. Internal electron donors are bonded directly to the MgCl₂ support and activate the site formation whereas the external electron donor could selectively poisons these sites[3–7]. The development of new electron donors is a challenging task and crucial of course for the scientists in designing advanced polypropylene catalysts.

The quantitative–structure activity/property relationship (QSAR/QSPR) is a proven technique to predict the desired activities/properties from the molecular properties and the paradigm of the model is “*Endpoint=f (molecular property)*”. A large number of molecular properties known as ‘descriptors’ are involved in building a good QSAR model. The QSAR/QSPR is also successfully applied for both homogenous[8–12] and heterogeneous catalysts[13–15]. This field helps in designing materials, screening of potential catalysts before the material being synthesised, minimizing the cost and can suggest mechanisms^[1, 16–20]. Good QSAR models could be built by known paradigms such as “*Endpoint=f (SMILES)*”,^[21, 22] “*Endpoint =f (quasi-SMILES)*”. The quasi-SMILES can be the representation of eclectic data, symbols of the SMILES structure/or groups in the molecular structure which can influence the property to a greater extent[23–25].

In the present paper attempts have been made to build QSPR models between adsorption energy (E_{ads}) in kcal/mol and optimal descriptors obtained from the quasi-SMILES codes of 29 internal electron donors, phthalates, 1,3-diethers and malonates

.Also, QSPR models built between polypropylene activity((kg PP/g Cat.) and optimal descriptors

2. Methods

2.1. Data

The dataset for the polypropylene activity (kg PP/g Cat.) and adsorption energy (E_{ads}) of 29 internal electron donors: Phthalates, 1, 3-diethers and Malonates is obtained from the published QSPR article [2]. The quasi code along with respective activity (kg PP/g Cat.) and adsorption energy were represented in the Table 1. The interprets of different quasi-SMILES code are listed in Table 2.

2.2. Descriptors and Methods of Monte Carlo Optimization

CORAL software (*Coral 1.5, 2010*; software available at <http://www.insilico.eu/coral>) is used for the Monte Carlo Optimization. The quasi-SMILES-based optimal descriptors are obtained using the following equation-I and described in detail by Toropov et al [26,27].

$$DCW(T, N) = \sum CW(S_k) \quad (1)$$

Where S_k is the quasi-SMILES attributes of the one and $CW(S_k)$ is correlation weights (CW_k). The Monte Carlo optimization building a QSPR model requires number of epochs to find a maximum of a target function. The target functions that are available in CORAL are (1) The classic scheme (CS), i.e., [training test, without calibration set] system; (2) balance of correlations (BC), i.e., [sub-training set, calibration set and test set] system; and (3) balance of correlations with ideal slopes (BCIS). The present

optimization process utilizes the above three methods is decently elaborated in the papers,[26,28] accordingly it is not depicted here.

Threshold T and N_{epoch} are the key parameters for the optimization process in order to build a good predictability QSAR/QSPR model with greater accuracy and precision [26,27]. The impact of these parameters in predicting the polypropylene activity(kg PP/g Cat.) and adsorption energy (E_{ads}) could be ascertained by the correlation coefficients (r^2) between experimental and predicted values for the sub-training set, calibration set and test set, described in detail in the subsequent result and discussions segment..

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Correlation weights (CWs) and optimal descriptor (DCW) Calculation

Table 3 lists correlation weights (CWs) of quasi-SMILES attributes for calculation of the optimal descriptor (DCW) for random split 3 for adsorption energy (Eq-11) and polypropylene activity (Eq.16) respectively. The CWs thus obtained can be used to calculate the optimal descriptors (DCWs) which is crucial parameter to build the QSPR models for the adsorption energy (kcal/mol) and polypropylene activity (kg PP/g Cat.). The calculation of DCW can be illustrated for diethyl phthalate (sample ID-2) with quasi-SMILES code '%10%12%12' for the Phthalates as internal donors for the random split-3 using CS method (Eq-11). The structural attribute '%10' and '%12' assigned CWs of 1.379 and 0.380 therefore DCW for '%10%12%12' is equal to 2.139 (1.379+ 0.380 + 0.380). Similarly, the optimal descriptors (DCWs) for all the quasi-SMILES codes is calculated using three methods *BC*, *BCIS* and *CS* for the different random splits and attempts have been made to build the following QSPR models for the adsorption

energy (kcal/mol) and polypropylene activity.

QSPR model-1 to model-9 were built based on their quasi-SMILES code based optimal descriptors for the adsorption energy for the three random splits using the three methods and QSPR model-10 to model-18 were built for the polypropylene activity (kg PP/g Cat.) are given below:

The quasi-SMILES based QSAR model for adsorption energy (E_{ads}) and PP activity can be represented by equation-1.

$$E_{ads} = C_0 + C_1 * DCW(T, N) \text{ or } PP \text{ activity} = C_0 + C_1 * DCW(T, N) \quad (2)$$

Where, intercept (C_0) and slope (C_1) can be calculated for each sub-training set, calibration set and validation set individually, T is the threshold and N is N_{epoch} . DCW is the optimal descriptor. Quasi-SMILES based QSAR models for the random split-1 to split- 4 are given below, that were built with the parameters: N_{epoch} 7 to 30; number of probes of optimization (P) is 3, threshold (T) 0 to 5, dr (weight) in method *BC* is 0.1, dC (weight) in method *BCIS* is 0.01, starting step of the optimization is $0.5 * CW$ (SA), the precision of the optimization is $0.01 * CW$ (SA).

The QSPR models (1, 4 and 7) that were built based on a *BC* method, models(2,5 and 8) based on a *BCIS* method and models(3,6 and 9) are based on the *CS* method for a split 1 to split 3 respectively. Statistical characteristics given below each of the QSPR model are: ' n ' are the number of internal donors in the set; ' r ' is correlation coefficient; ' Q ' is cross-validated correlation coefficients; ' s ' is the standard error of estimation; *MAE* is mean absolute error and ' f ' is Fischer F-ratio.

QSPR model-1 for random split-1 by *BC* method

$$E_{ads} = 13.265 (\pm 0.318) + 2.087 (\pm 0.098) * DCW (3, 15) (3)$$

$n=10$, $r^2 = 0.801$, $Q^2 = 0.723$, $s = 3.07$, $MAE = 2.62$ and $f = 32$ (sub-training set)

$n=5$, $r^2 = 0.908$, $Q^2 = 0.773$, $s = 5.23$, $MAE = 4.10$ and $f = 30$ (calibration set)

$n=6$, $r^2 = 0.911$, $Q^2 = 0.500$, $s = 2.63$, $MAE = 1.78$ and $f = 41$ (validation set)

$n=8$, $r^2 = 0.87$, $Q^2 = 0.838$, $s = 2.59$, $MAE = 1.59$, (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-2 for random split-1 by *BCIS* method

$$E_{ads} = 0.166 (\pm 0.803) + 5.016 (\pm 0.233) * DCW (3,30) (4)$$

$n=10$, $r^2 = 0.818$, $Q^2 = 0.744$, $s = 2.94$, $MAE = 2.50$ and $f = 36$ (sub-training set)

$n=5$, $r^2 = 0.882$, $Q^2 = 0.727$, $s = 5.01$, $MAE = 3.90$ and $f = 22$ (calibration set)

$n=6$, $r^2 = 0.851$, $Q^2 = 0.437$, $s = 2.81$, $MAE = 1.87.72$ and $f = 23$ (validation set)

$n=8$, $r^2 = 0.861$, $Q^2 = 0.838$, $s = 2.63$, $MAE = 1.61$, (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-3 for random split-1 by *CS* method

$$E_{ads} = 4.460 (\pm 0.351) + 4.718 (\pm 0.101) * DCW(1,30) (5)$$

$n=15$, $r^2 = 0.918$, $Q^2 = 0.895$, $s = 1.90$, $MAE = 1.24$ and $f = 147$ (sub-training set)

$n=6$, $r^2 = 0.869$, $Q^2 = 0.506$, $s = 7.85$, $MAE = 6.69$ and $f = 27$ (validation set)

$n=8$, $r^2 = 0.836$, $Q^2 = 0.806$, $s = 4.74$, $MAE = 3.74$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-4 for random split-2 by *BC* method

$$E_{ads} = 11.678 (\pm 0.036) + 1.614 (\pm 0.007) * DCW(1,30) (6)$$

$n=10$, $r^2 = 0.999$, $Q^2 = 0.998$, $s = 0.168$, $MAE = 0.74$ and $f = 8843$ (sub-training set)

$n=5$, $r^2 = 0.998$, $Q^2 = 0.995$, $s = 6.95$, $MAE = 6.15$ and $f = 4051$ (calibration set)

$n=6, r^2=0.926, Q^2=0.834, s=5.63, MAE=4.24$ and $f=51$ (validation set)

$n=8, r^2=0.876, Q^2=0.863, s=5.15, MAE=4.03$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-5 for random split-2 by *BCIS* method

$$E_{ads} = -0.357 (\pm 0.333) + 6.793 (\pm 0.106) * DCW(1,30) \quad (7)$$

$n=10, r^2=0.985, Q^2=0.977, s=0.67, MAE=0.52$ and $f=539$ (sub-training set)

$n=5, r^2=0.980, Q^2=0.935, s=8.86, MAE=7.89$ and $f=149$ (calibration set)

$n=6, r^2=0.875, Q^2=0.633, s=6.46, MAE=5.104$ and $f=28$ (validation set)

$n=8, r^2=0.766, Q^2=0.761, s=6.94, MAE=5.59$ (invisible validation set)

SPR model-6 for random split-2 by *CS* method

$$E_{ads} = 15.480 (\pm 0.086) + 2.490 (\pm 0.032) * DCW(3,30) \quad (8)$$

$n=15, r^2=0.690, Q^2=0.625, s=3.15, MAE=2.46$ and $f=29$ (sub-training set)

$n=6, r^2=0.721, Q^2=0.433, s=5.44, MAE=4.37$ and $f=10$ (validation set)

$n=8, r^2=0.624, Q^2=0.212, s=4.41, MAE=3.34$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-7 for random split-3 by *BC* method

$$E_{ads} = 10.078 (\pm 0.095) + 2.093 (\pm 0.013) * DCW(1,30) \quad (9)$$

$n=16, r^2=0.997, Q^2=0.995, s=0.306, MAE=0.24$ and $f=2256$ (sub-training set)

$n=5, r^2=0.998, Q^2=0.995, s=6.34, MAE=4.41$ and $f=2260$ (calibration set)

$n=8, r^2=0.922, Q^2=0.782, s=7.46, MAE=6.54$ and $f=48$ (validation set)

$n=8, r^2=0.921, Q^2=0.879, s=4.99, MAE=3.86$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-8 for random split-3 by *BCIS* method

$$E_{ads} = -0.022 (\pm 0.7196379) + 2.709 (\pm 0.084) * DCW(1,30) \quad (10)$$

$n=16, r^2=0.970, Q^2=0.946, s=0.96, MAE=0.638$ and $f=260$ (sub-training set)

$n=5, r^2=0.928, Q^2=0.789, s=7.37, MAE=5.75$ and $f=39$ (calibration set)

$n=8, r^2=0.915, Q^2=0.588, s=9.96, MAE=8.97$ and $f=43$ (validation set)

$n=8, r^2=0.626, Q^2=0.604, s=8.00, MAE=6.33$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-9 for random split-3 by *CS* method

$$E_{ads} = 7.290 (\pm 0.259) + 4.822 (\pm 0.096) * DCW (1, 30) \quad (11)$$

$n=21$, $r^2 = 0.921$, $Q^2 = 0.900$, $s = 1.89$, $MAE = 1.17$ and $f = 153$ (sub-training set)

$n=8$, $r^2 = 0.849$, $Q^2 = 0.651$, $s = 7.21$, $MAE = 5.88$ and $f = 22$ (validation set)

$n=8$, $r^2 = 0.530$, $Q^2 = 0.524$, $s = 7.08$, $MAE = 5.64$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR models for the polypropylene activity using the three methods are given below:

QSPR model-10 for PP activity by *BC* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = -7.932 (\pm 0.747) + 3.851 (\pm 0.150) * DCW (1,5) \quad (12)$$

$n=10$, $r^2 = 0.955$, $Q^2 = 0.918$, $s = 2.13$, $MAE = 1.62$ and $f = 170$ (sub-training set)

$n=5$, $r^2 = 0.956$, $Q^2 = 0.840$, $s = 12.3$, $MAE = 9.96$ and $f = 65$ (calibration set)

$n=6$, $r^2 = 0.775$, $Q^2 = 0.650$, $s = 15.1$, $MAE = 13.1$ and $f = 14$ (validation set)

$n=8$, $r^2 = 0.630$, $Q^2 = 0.433$, $s = 13.06$, $MAE = 11.20$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-11 for PP activity by *BCIS* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = -0.032 (\pm 0.845) + 2.388 (\pm 0.163) * DCW (1, 5) \quad (13)$$

$n=10$, $r^2 = 0.876$, $Q^2 = 0.774$, $s = 3.56$, $MAE = 1.97$ and $f = 56$ (sub-training set)

$n=5$, $r^2 = 0.943$, $Q^2 = 0.822$, $s = 6.30$, $MAE = 4.97$ and $f = 50$ (calibration set)

$n=6$, $r^2 = 0.872$, $Q^2 = 0.802$, $s = 10.4$, $MAE = 9.08$ and $f = 27$ (validation set)

$n=8$, $r^2 = 0.635$, $Q^2 = 0.623$, $s = 9.97$, $MAE = 8.62$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-12 for PP activity by *CS* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = -11.436 (\pm 0.818) + 7.022 (\pm 0.211) * DCW (1,5) \quad (14)$$

$n=15$, $r^2 = 0.904$, $Q^2 = 0.868$, $s = 2.83$, $MAE = 1.86$ and $f = 124$ (sub-training set)

$n=6$, $r^2 = 0.918$, $Q^2 = 0.848$, $s = 12.10$, $MAE = 10.6$ and $f = 45$ (validation set)

$n=8, r^2=0.525, Q^2=0.501, s=10.87, MAE=9.43$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-13 for PP activity by *BC* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = 0.690 (\pm 0.267) + 6.487 (\pm 0.101) * DCW (1,5) \quad (15)$$

$n=19, r^2=0.966, Q^2=0.954, s=1.79, MAE=1.20$ and $f=256$ (sub-training set)

$n=5, r^2=0.989, Q^2=0.974, s=9.74, MAE=8.63$ and $f=295$ (calibration set)

$n=5, r^2=0.610, Q^2=0.446, s=21.2, MAE=9.28$ and $f=15$ (validation set)

QSPR model-14 for PP activity by *BCIS method*

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = -0.0589 (\pm 0.680) + 4.006 (\pm 0.099) * DCW (1,5) \quad (16)$$

$n=19, r^2=0.892, Q^2=0.858, s=3.17, MAE=1.95$ and $f=75$ (sub-training set)

$n=5, r^2=0.982, Q^2=0.959, s=1.09, MAE=0.69$ and $f=167$ (calibration set)

$n=5, r^2=0.979, Q^2=-1.735, s=16.50, MAE=12.1$ and $f=6$ (validation set)

$n=8, r^2=0.688, Q^2=0.659, s=6.64, MAE=5.39$ (invisible validation set)

QSPR model-15 for PP activity by *CS* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = 3.671 (\pm 0.288) + 3.157 (\pm 0.052) * DCW (1,3) \quad (17)$$

$n=16, r^2=0.922, Q^2=0.904, s=2.49, MAE=1.70$ and $f=167$ (sub-training set)

$n=5, r^2=0.636, Q^2=-2.081, s=12.8, MAE=8.43$ and $f=5$ (validation set)

QSPR model-16 for PP activity by *BC* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = 10.873 (\pm 0.771) + 1.223 (\pm 0.124) * DCW (1,5) \quad (18)$$

$n=9, r^2= 0.727, Q^2= 0. 545, s= 4. 28, MAE= 2.71$ and $f= 19$ (sub-training set)

$n=6, r^2= 0.980, Q^2= 0.946, s= 3.52, MAE=2.42$ and $f= 205$ (calibration set)

$n=6, r^2= 0.813, Q^2= 0.438, s=8.37, MAE= 7.13$ and $f= 17$ (validation set)

QSPR model-17 for PP activity by *BCIS* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = -0.0042 (\pm 0.843) + 2.568 (\pm 0.134) * DCW \quad (1,7) \quad (9)$$

$n=9, r^2= 0.799, Q^2= 0. 712, s= 3. 67, MAE= 2.20$ and $f= 28$ (sub-training set)

$n=6, r^2= 0.800, Q^2= 0.537, s= 4.73, MAE=4.04$ and $f= 16$ (calibration set)

$n=6, r^2= 0.790, Q^2= 0.430, s=11.5, MAE= 10.2$ and $f= 15$ (validation set)

QSPR model-18 for PP activity by *CS* method

$$PP_{\text{activity}} = 9.085 (\pm 0.329) + 2.595 (\pm 0.118) * DCW \quad (1, 3) \quad (20)$$

$n=15, r^2= 0.888, Q^2= 0. 822, s= 2. 76, MAE= 2.05$ and $f= 103$ (sub-training set)

$n=6, r^2= 0.681, Q^2= 0.164, s=10.0, MAE=8.54$ and $f= 9$ (validation set)

The intercept (C_0) values lie between 10.078 to 13.265 and slope (C_1) 1.614 to 2.093 for the random splits 1 to 3 respectively by the *BC* method in the models for E_{ads} . The intercept (C_0) values lie between -0.022 to 0.166 and slope (C_1) 2.709 to 6.793 for the random split 1 to 3 respectively by the *BCIS* method for E_{ads} . The C_0 lies between 4.460 and 15.480 and slope (C_1) lies between 2.490 and 4.822 for the models

by the CS method for E_{ads} . Now, for *PP* activity models the model constants: the intercept (C_0) values lie between -7.932 to 10.873 and slope (C_1) 1.223 to 6.487 by the *BC* method. The intercept (C_0) values lie between -0.0058 to -0.0042 and slope (C_1) 2.388 to 4.006 by the *BCIS* method. The C_0 lies between 3.671 and 9.085 and slope (C_1) lies between 2.595 and 7.022 for the models by the CS method.

Table 4 lists the experimental and predicted adsorption energy (kcal/mol) by QPPR model-4 (Eq.6) with the experimental and predicted polypropylene Activity (kg PP/g Cat.) by QPPR model-16(Eq.18) along with their corresponding optimal descriptors (DCWs). The average values for statistical characteristics of Monte Carlo optimization for the random split-2 by *BC*, *BCIS* and *CS* methods are listed in Table 5.

3.2 External validation Characteristics of the QSPR models

Y-scrambling technique[29] is employed to check the robustness of all the QSPR models[29]. The randomization parameter $^c r_p^2$ where $^c r_p^2 = r(r^2 - r_r^2)^{1/2}$ is average randomized r obtained by Y- Scrambling probe.

The QSPR study always hints at reducing the noise is an important feature in building a better model and if $^c r_p^2$ greater than 0.5 then the given QSAR model is considered to be robust[29]. The meaning of 1 probe of the randomization is the random shuffling of 100 calculated end points (E_{ads} or *PP* activity) without any change in the column of experimental values. External validation characteristics such as 'k', which should be $0.85 < k < 1.15$, [30] 'kk' should be $0.85 < kk < 1.15$, [30] r_m^2 and r_m^{*2} both should be greater than 0.5 ($r_m^2(x, y)$, $r_m^{*2}(y, x)$) obtained where x, y are experimental and predicted values of E_{ads} . [31] Average $r_m^2 > 0.5$ [32] and $\Delta r_m^2 < 0.2$

[32]. Table 6 lists the external validation characteristics of the eighteen QSPR models (1 to 9 for E_{ads} and 10 to 18 for PP activity. QSPR model 1,2 for adsorption energy (kcal/mol) fulfils all the external validation criteria and therefore these models are robust.

3.3 Comparison of the quasi-SMILES QSPR models with other QSPR models

Quantitative Structure Property Relationship (QSPR) for adsorption energies was reported by Ratanasak et al[2] for a set of 24 compounds from 3 different groups, i.e., phthalates, 1,3-diethers and malonates using the multiple linear regression (MLR) analysis. They reported that the best QSPR model showed a high correlation ($r^2 = 0.84$) between adsorption energies and 3 descriptors, i.e., the radius of gyration (50%), the dipole moment (16%), and the Forcite bond energy (34%)[2]. The other two models of adsorption energy reported have $r^2=0.66$ (single descriptor 'bond energy') and $r^2 = 0.84$ (two descriptor model 'bond energy' and 'radius of gyration'). Moreover, the authors of the paper showed that the standard deviation(s) of the three-descriptor model ($s=2.61$), two descriptor model ($s = 2.79$). The Fischer F-ratio (f) of their three descriptor model ($f = 64.00$) and that of two descriptor model ($f=54.44$). The best models for the adsorption energy in the present paper are model-1, QSPR model-4 obtained from the random split-2 by BC method, for the training set ($r^2= 0.999$, $s= 0.168$, $f= 8843$). The randomization parameter are 0.97, 0.90 and 0.78 for sub-training set, calibration set and validation set respectively, r_m^2 , r_m^{*2} , $r_m^2(Avg)$ and Δr_m^2 are 0.81,0.88,0.84 and 0.07 respectively(Table 6) justifies the robustness of the model.

Now, the statistical parameters and external validation characteristics of the model between adsorption energy and single optimal descriptor (DCW) which is

derived from the quasi-SMILES codes of three internal donors appears to be better than that are obtained using the multiple linear regression (MLR) analysis[2]. Similarly, model-16 between polypropylene activity (kg PP/g Cat.) and quasi-SMILES code by the balance of correlation method with good statistical parameter and external validation characteristics (Table 6) appears to be robust.

3.4 Application of quasi-SMILES based QSPR model for designing new internal donors Ziegler – Natta catalyzed propylene polymerization

Can we design new electron donors with any of the quasi-SMILES based QSPR model ? Owing to the fact that adsorption energies(E_{ads}) of electron donors to catalyst surface are linearly related to activities, model-4 with good statistical, external validation characteristics, is chosen to design new electron donors and predict the adsorption energy(kcal/mol) for the catalyst. The malonates are showing better adsorption energy. The malonate with quasi-SMILES code (%27%20%20%17) is dibutyl malonate, where ‘%17’ represents butyl (E_{ads} =16.36 kcal/mol, $PP_{activity}$ =0.3kg PP/g Cat., Table 1), when the code is replaced to %27%20%20%18 it becomes diisonoyl malonate(‘%18’ represents isononyl), E_{ads} is 17.91 kcal/mol predicted by the model-4. Table 7 lists the newly designed 24 malonates as internal donors for propylene polymerization with their name, quasi-SMILES codes and predicted adsorption energies in kcal/mol by the model-4. The malonates like ‘diisononyl dibutyl malonate’ are showed good adsorption energy greater than 25.00kcal/mol).

The supplementary materials file contains Tables 1S which lists experimental and predicted Adsorption energy(kcal/mol) by QSPR model-1 to model-9 the three random splits. Table 2S which lists experimental and predicted polypropylene activity (kg PP/g Cat.) by QSPR model-10 to model 18. Table 3S to Table 18S lists the correlations weights used in different QSPR models.

4. Conclusions

The present paper discusses about the QSPR between adsorption energies and quasi-SMILES codes of 29 internal donors of the ZN catalyzed propylene polymerization, i.e. phthalate, 1, 3-diether and malonate. The best model for the adsorption energy in the present paper could be obtained from the random split-2 by balance of correlations method. The statistical parameters together with the external validation characteristics of the model-4 for the adsorption energy of internal donors of the ZN catalyzed propylene polymerization prove to be robust. Similarly, model-16 between polypropylene activity (kg PP/g Cat.) and quasi-SMILES code by the balance of correlation method displayed better statistical parameter, randomization parameter and external validation characteristics. Hence, it can be concluded here that the quasi-SMILES based QSPR modelling for the adsorption energy, pp activity or in any field of catalysis, is definitely, an alternate option (to be explored more and more) to the models built by traditional means such as MLR, neural network etc. The quasi-SMILES based QSPR model successfully applied for designing new internal donors for the ZN catalyzed propylene polymerization.

Acknowledgements

The author expresses his appreciation to the Centre of Excellence in Theoretical and Mathematical Sciences of, Siksha 'O' Anusandhan University, Khandagiri, and Bhubaneswar for extending the computational facility.

References

- [1] T. Taniike, M. Terano, *Coadsorption model for first-principle description of roles of donors in heterogeneous Ziegler–Natta propylene polymerization*, J. Catal. 293 (2012), pp. 39–50.

- [2] M. Ratanasak, T. Rungrotmongkol, O. Saengsawang, S. Hannongbua, V. Parasuk, *Towards the design of new electron donors for Ziegler–Natta catalyzed propylene polymerization using QSPR modeling*, *Polymer (Guildf)*. 56 (2015), pp. 340–345.
- [3] U. Makwana, D.G. Naik, G. Singh, V. Patel, H.R. Patil, V.K. Gupta, *Nature of Phthalates as Internal Donors in High Performance MgCl₂ Supported Titanium Catalysts*, *Catal.Letters*.131 (2009), pp. 624–631.
- [4] K. Matyjaszewski, S. Gaynor, D. Greszta, D. Mardare, T. Shigemoto, *Synthesis of well defined polymers by controlled radical polymerization*, *Macromol. Symp.* 98 (1995), pp. 73–89.
- [5] M.C. Sacchi, I. Tritto, P. Locatelli, *Stereochemical investigation of the effect of Lewis bases in heterogeneous Ziegler–Natta initiator systems*, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 16 (1991), pp. 331–360.
- [6] J. Xu, L. Feng, and S. Yang, *Formation Mechanism of Stereoblocks in Polypropylene Produced by Supported Ziegler–Natta Catalysts*, *Macromolecules*. 30 (1997), pp. 2539–2541.
- [7] E. Albizzati, U. Giannini, G. Morini, M. Galimberti, L. Barino, R. Scordamaglia, *Recent advances in propylene polymerization with MgCl₂ supported catalysts*, *Macromol. Symp.* 89 (1995), pp. 73–89.
- [8] S. Yao, T. Shoji, Y. Iwamoto, E. Kamei, *Consideration of an activity of the metallocene catalyst by using molecular mechanics, molecular dynamics and QSAR*, *Comput. Theor. Polym. Sci.* 9 (1999), pp. 41–46.
- [9] S. Martínez, V.L. Cruz, J. Ramos, J. Martínez-Salazar, *Polymerization Activity Prediction of Zirconocene Single-Site Catalysts Using 3D Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship Modeling*, *Organometallics*. 31 (2012), pp. 1673–1679.
- [10] V.L. Cruz, J. Martinez, J. Martinez-Salazar, J. Ramos, M.L. Reyes, A. Toro-Labbe, et al., *QSAR model for ethylene polymerisation catalysed by supported bis(imino)pyridine iron complexes*, *Polymer (Guildf)*. 48 (2007), pp. 7672–7678.
- [11] V.L. Cruz, J. Ramos, S. Martinez, A. Muñoz-Escalona, and J. Martinez-Salazar, *Structure–Activity Relationship Study of the Metallocene Catalyst Activity in Ethylene Polymerization*, *Organometallics*. 24 (2005), pp. 5095–5102.
doi:10.1021/om050458f.

- [12] V. Cruz, J. Ramos, A. Muñoz-Escalona, P. Lafuente, B. Peña, J. Martínez-Salazar, *3D-QSAR analysis of metallocene-based catalysts used in ethylene polymerisation*, Polymer (Guildf). 45 (2004) ,pp. 2061–2072.
- [13] V.L. Cruz, S. Martínez, J. Martínez-Salazar, D. Polo-Cerón, S. Gómez-Ruiz, M. Fajardo, et al., *3D-QSAR study of ansa-metallocene catalytic behavior in ethylene polymerization*, Polymer (Guildf). 48 (2007) ,pp. 4663–4674.
- [14] G. Fayet, P. Raybaud, H. Toulhoat, T. de Bruin, *Iron bis(arylimino)pyridine precursors activated to catalyze ethylene oligomerization as studied by DFT and QSAR approaches*, J. Mol. Struct. THEOCHEM. 903 (2009) ,pp. 100–107.
- [15] V. Tognetti, G. Fayet, C. Adamo, *Can molecular quantum descriptors predict the butene selectivity in nickel(II) catalyzed ethylene dimerization? A QSPR study*, Int. J. Quantum Chem. 110 (2010),pp. 540–548.
- [16] Z. Boudene, T. De Bruin, H. Toulhoat, P. Raybaud, *A QSPR Investigation of Thermal Stability of [Al(CH₃)O]_n Oligomers in Methylaluminoxane Solution: The Identification of a Geometry-Based Descriptor*, Organometallics. 31 (2012) ,pp. 8312–8322.
- [17] T.A. Manz, J.M. Caruthers, S. Sharma, K. Phomphrai, K.T. Thomson, W.N. Delgass, et al., *Structure–Activity Correlation for Relative Chain Initiation to Propagation Rates in Single-Site Olefin Polymerization Catalysis*, Organometallics. 31 (2012). pp. 602–618.
- [18] D. Wu, C. Wang, B. Liu, D. Liu, Q. Yang, C. Zhong, *Large-scale computational screening of metal-organic frameworks for CH₄/H₂ separation*, AIChE J. 58 (2012),pp. 2078–2084.
- [19] L.M. Colosi, Q. Huang, W.J. Weber, *QSAR-assisted design of an environmental catalyst for enhanced estrogen remediation*, Chemosphere. 81 (2010),pp. 897–903.
- [20] F. di Lena, C.L.L. Chai, *Quantitative structure-reactivity modeling of copper-catalyzed atom transfer radical polymerization*, Polym. Chem. 1 (2010),pp.922–930.
- [21] P.G.R. Achary, *QSPR modelling of dielectric constants of π -conjugated organic compounds by means of the CORAL software*, SAR QSAR Environ. Res. 25 (2014), pp. 507–526.

- [22] S. Begum, P.G.R. Achary, *Simplified molecular input line entry system-based: QSAR modelling for MAP kinase-interacting protein kinase (MNKI)*, SAR QSAR Environ. Res. 26 (2015), pp. 343–361.
- [23] A.A. Toropov, A.P. Toropova, T. Puzyn, E. Benfenati, G. Gini, D. Leszczynska, et al., *QSAR as a random event: modeling of nanoparticles uptake in PaCa2 cancer cells.*, Chemosphere. 92 (2013), pp. 31–7.
doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.03.012.
- [24] A.A. Toropov, A.P. Toropova, *Optimal descriptor as a translator of eclectic data into endpoint prediction: mutagenicity of fullerene as a mathematical function of conditions.* Chemosphere. 104 (2014), pp. 262–4.
- [25] A.P. Toropova, A.A. Toropov, *Optimal descriptor as a translator of eclectic information into the prediction of membrane damage by means of various TiO(2) nanoparticles.*, Chemosphere. 93 (2013), pp. 2650–5.
- [26] A.P. Toropova, A.A. Toropov, A. Lombardo, A. Roncaglioni, E. Benfenati, G. Gini, *A new bioconcentration factor model based on SMILES and indices of presence of atoms.*, Eur. J. Med. Chem. 45 (2010), pp. 4399–402.
- [27] A.A. Toropov, A.P. Toropova, E. Benfenati, *SMILES-based optimal descriptors: QSAR modeling of carcinogenicity by balance of correlations with ideal slopes.*, Eur. J. Med. Chem. 45 (2010), pp. 3581–7.
- [28] A.P. Toropova, A.A. Toropov, E. Benfenati, G. Gini, D. Leszczynska, J. Leszczynski, *CORAL: QSPR models for solubility of [C60] and [C70] fullerene derivatives*, Mol. Divers. 15 (2010), pp. 249–256. doi:10.1007/s11030-010-9245-6.
- [29] P.K. Ojha, K. Roy, *Comparative QSARs for antimalarial endochins: Importance of descriptor-thinning and noise reduction prior to feature selection*, Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst. 109 (2011), pp. 146–161. doi:10.1016/j.chemolab.2011.08.007.
- [30] A. Golbraikh, A. Tropsha, *Beware of q²!*, J. Mol. Graph. Model. 20 (2002), pp. 269–276.
- [31] P.P. Roy, K. Roy, *QSAR Studies of CYP2D6 Inhibitor Aryloxypropanolamines Using 2D and 3D Descriptors*, Chem. Biol. Drug Des. 73 (2009), pp. 442–455.
- [32] P.K. Ojha, I. Mitra, R.N. Das, K. Roy, *Further exploring rm2 metrics for validation of QSPR models*, Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst. 107 (2011), pp. 94–205.

List of Tables

Table 1. *Quasi SMILES code with Polypropylene Activity (kg PP/g Cat.) and Adsorption energy(kcal/mol)[2]*

Table 2 : Quasi-SMILES code with their interprets
Table 3. Correlation weights(CWs) of quasi-SMILES attributes for calculation of the optimal descriptor(DCW) for random split 3 used for adsorption energy (kcal/mol (Eq-11) and polypropylene activity (kg PP/g Cat.) (Eq.16)

Table 4. Experimental and Predicted Adsorption energy (kcal/mol) by QPPR model-4 and model-6 with Polypropylene Activity (kg PP/g Cat.) by QPPR model-16 with their corresponding optimal descriptors(DCWs)

Table 5. The average values for statistical characteristics of Monte Carlo optimization for the random by *BC*, *BCIS* and *CS* methods

Table 6. External validation characteristics for the Quasi-SMILES based QSPR models for the Adsorption energy (kcal/mol) and Polypropylene Activity (kg PP/g Cat.) of 29 electron donors

Table 7. Application of quasi-SMILES based QSPR model for designing new internal donors Ziegler– Natta catalyzed propylene polymerization with the predicted E_{ads}